

SINGLE-MODE PERFORMANCE OF STAMPED METALLIC FIBER-OPTIC TURNING MIRROR ARRAYS FOR WDM LAN AND RF-OVER-FIBER APPLICATIONS

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Introduction

The aerospace environment presents a formidable research and engineering challenge for designing, packaging and qualifying components for avionics-grade, active and passive, single-mode wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) [1]. New optoelectronic package interface and optical subassembly designs are currently under development for single-mode avionics WDM local area network (WDM LAN) as well as RF-over-fiber application modules [2-4]. Further, stamped metal components with nanometer-scale dimensional tolerances can miniaturize, increase the density, and reduce the cost of packages for single-mode WDM LAN and RF-over-fiber modules for commercial and aerospace applications [5].

Stamped Metallic Micro-Mirror Arrays and Multi-Fiber Connectors

We developed a manufacturing process to produce arrays of micro turning mirrors, monolithically stamped into metal bodies, Figure 1(a), for coupling optical fibers to silicon and III-V photonic single-mode sources/detectors, and vice-versa [6]. These low-profile mirror arrays have a thickness of less than 1.5 mm for use in low-profile packages, and the body is made of Kovar, which is rugged and has a close CTE match to semiconductors. A single mirror accomplishes the $\approx 90^\circ$ turn, focusing, and mode conversion from source-to-fiber. The stamped mirror's figure/form error is generally less than ~ 400 nm as shown by the scanning white light interferometry data shown in Figure 1(b).

Figure 1: Stamped, micro mirror array for single-mode grating couplers, 250 μm pitch, and low BER at 25 Gbps. (a) 8-channel and (b) 4-channel measured deviation < 400 nm for stamped mirror array.

Figure 2(a) shows validation test data to verify the optical design of the single-mode mirrors by coupling light into SM fibers. The mirrors were stamped into pure aluminum with a reflectivity of 94% (-0.27 dB), and the total insertion loss was 0.72 dB. Only 0.09 dB was attributed to mirror figure error. Figure 2b shows the test configuration for assessing all eight channels in the stamped array using one SM fiber as source. Results for four mirror arrays are listed in Table 1. The average and worst IL were -0.70 dB and -1.16 dB, respectively, for all 32 channels. These mirror arrays were also tested with a single-mode silicon-photonics 100 Gbps transceiver in which the mirrors coupled single-mode fibers to the chip's grating couplers; the modulation rate was 25 Gbps for each of four wavelengths.

	Power (mW)	Power (dBm)	Loss (dB)	Loss (%)
Measured source power	1.00	0.00		
Reflectivity of aluminum			-0.27	94
Efficiency at fiber facet			-0.36	92
Efficiency of mirror form			-0.09	98
Total predicted loss			-0.72	85
Predicted power	0.85	-0.72		
Measured power	0.85	-0.72		
Discrepancy	0.00	0.0		

Figure 2a: Contributions to the insertion loss.

Figure 2b: IL test configuration.

The mil/aero environments for WDM and RF-over-fiber also require a rugged multi-fiber ferrule. High-precision stamping also enabled a novel multi-fiber connector that is a less expensive and more rugged than the polymer MT ferrule. The FootballFerrule®, shown in Figure 3, is made of stainless steel 316L [7] and small enough that it fits between the alignment pin holes of an MT ferrule. FootballFerrules are aligned with a compliant alignment sleeve due to the precise control of the form and size of the ferrule outer body, and this eliminates the need for expensive alignment pins which damage the MT ferrule.

Table 1: Insertion loss for four 8-channel mirror arrays

CH	SN			
	8MOB8014	8MOB8018	8MOB8016	8MOB8020
1	-0.65	-0.67	-0.70	-0.41
2	-0.48	-0.57	-0.42	-0.57
3	-0.51	-0.58	-1.16	-0.50
4	-0.64	-0.74	-1.05	-0.96
5	-0.84	-0.52	-0.67	-1.08
6	-0.73	-0.54	-0.92	-0.69
7	-0.53	-0.34	-0.84	-0.66
8	-0.54	-0.93	-1.14	-0.84

Figure 3: FootballFerrule® and MT ferrule.

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